

The Influence of Product Quality, Price, Promotion, Lifestyle, and E-WOM On Purchase Decision of Thrift Apparel Mediated by Purchase Intention.

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to determine the influence of product quality, price, promotion, lifestyle, and eWOM on purchasing decisions for thrift clothing which is mediated by purchase intention. The method used in this research can be grouped as comparative causal research, namely research to see the effect of one variable on another. This type of research. In this research, the research object that will be used is the people of Batam City. The samples used were residents of Batam City who had purchased Thrift clothing, either online (Instagram, Shopee, Ecommerce) or who had made purchases by coming directly to the Thrifting place (Thrift Market/Second Market). The results obtained from this research are that Product Quality has no significant influence on Purchase decisions, Price has no significant influence on Purchase decisions, Lifestyle has no significant influence on Purchase decisions, Promotion has a direct influence on Purchase Decisions, E-WOM has a direct influence on Purchase Decisions, E-WOM has a direct influence on Purchase Intention. Purchase Intention has a direct influence on Purchase Decision. Purchase Intention has a direct influence on Purchase Decision.

KEYWORDS: Product Quality, Price, Promotion, Lifestyle, Electronik Word of Mouth, Purchase Decision, Purchase intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of globalization today, the phenomenon that is affecting people's lives today is consumer behavior. This is influenced by the lifestyle and habits of society, especially in terms of fashion or appearance, people tend to behave consumptive. Consumer habits that cannot be predicted easily have an impact on the increasingly developing business world, one of which is business clothes. Customers will tend to be interested so that a product marketed in the community can adapt to their tastes and lifestyle and their needs. Consumers who have been influenced by consumer culture will be willing to do anything to meet their clothing needs, therefore, business people must be able to read and understand the ongoing consumer behavior. develop. As the use of the internet develops, many people's lives depend on the internet. With the internet, a lot of people who use it as a platform to create trends that can be easily followed by the wider community. The internet has many impacts on its users, including people's clothing habits. If there is a trend on the internet to wear 80's and 90's themed clothing, consumers will compete to follow this trend so that they don't look out of date. The high level of competition in the world of fashion has made many people flock to look fashionable by following existing fashion trends.

Clothing is one of the primary needs that underlies human life to survive. Clothing is intended to protect the body from heat, cold and dust and dirt. According to Dewi & Mahargiono (2022) Nowadays, clothing which was originally a primary need has also become a tertiary need. Tertiary needs are needs that can be avoided in human life, such as means of transportation, communication tools, and luxury goods/jewelry. Communities that can fulfill tertiary needs are usually seen as superior or receive a higher degree. Therefore, people compete to fulfill tertiary needs such as clothing to meet their lifestyle needs. Consumers want to wear luxury and branded clothing. Many clothing stores offer products with different models and brands due to the high demand related to the world of fashion (Andriani & Menuk Sri, 2021). However, nowadays many people ignore the clothes they buy new or used, they only focus on the brands and models offered. In fulfilling these needs, the term 'Thrifting'. Thrifting is the trend of buying used clothes that are suitable for use. Sales of thrifting clothes can now be done online or offline. Before selling used clothes that are suitable for use, they will be sorted first.

The thrifting phenomenon in Indonesia is spreading very quickly among millennials. Lifestyle demands mean that many millennial generations try to follow trends. According to data from the results of a survey conducted by Goodstats (Naurah, 2022), involving 261 respondents. 49.4% of respondents had purchased fashion products from thrifting, around 34.5% had never thrifted, and 16.1% chose never to thrift. Used clothes are an alternative for the younger generation to still look fashionable but spend little. Price offered Thrift clothing products are also relatively cheap. The types of clothing presented in thrift products also vary, such as jackets,

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t-shirts, trousers, dresses, shirts, sweaters, skirts, and tops. In addition, there are various types of brands and brands on offer. Therefore, many consumers are very interested in thriftshopping.

Figure 1. Survey data of respondents who engage in thrifting.

The issue of thrifting is being discussed intensively because of the pros and cons it raises. The rapid growth of fashion development has given rise to many social and environmental problems. Production of clothing products has increased very rapidly, causing clothing prices to become cheaper and people's purchasing power to increase (Farah Fu et al., 2022). For example, well-known foreign brands such as Zara, HnM, Uniqlo will release clothes based on the season. To increase sales, the brand will hold price cuts. As a result of this activity, there is a large accumulation of clothing waste from consumers. In overcoming this problem, a thrifting campaign emerged. Thrifting is one effort to overcome fast fashion consumer behavior in reducing fashion waste. According to Nidia & Suhartini (2020) Fast fashion is a form of business model that offers trendy clothing but at very affordable prices. As technology develops, thrift stores are not only available in markets, but also in online stores.

Batam city is one of the thrifting centers in Indonesia, both through online stores and offline stores (Ristiani et al., 2022). There are reasons that make consumers interested in thrift clothing, namely:

1. There are various branded brands at low prices.
2. Quality items in very good condition
3. Very cheap clothing prices

The large number of well-known brand products being bought and sold makes thrift clothing in Batam attract a lot of consumer attention. Such as brands Supreme, Balenciaga, Adidas, and so on which are sold original. When compared with the new price, there will be a very big difference. Therefore, many consumers choose to thrift as an alternative to dressing fashionably and trendily. Apart from that, the items presented come in varied models and are rarely available on the market. The increasing culture of thrifting will certainly have an impact on the environment and society. Apart from threatening the country's economy, thrift products also endanger health. According to research by the Ministry of Trade in Wijaya & Dian Andriasari (2022) Several bacteria were found on thrift clothing such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and other types of fungi which can cause digestive disorders, acne, boils, skin infections, even urinary tract infections, in one sample there were around 216,000 bacteria found.

Apart from health issues, the law also regulates the trade in thrift products. The Ministry of Trade appealed to the public not to buy or use second-hand imported clothing by issuing Minister of Trade Regulation Number 51/M-DAG/PER/7/2015. This regulation aims to protect consumers from diseases and bacteria carried on these clothes. Apart from protecting the public from the health threats posed by Thrift clothing, the government also protects the country's economy. With the threat of a recession occurring, the textile industry in Indonesia is competing with imported products on the domestic market. According to API or the Indonesian Textile Association, it asked the government to immediately stop the sale of imported used clothing products. This can have a big impact on the textile industry ecosystem in Indonesia. There is a ban on importing used clothes because according to BPS import export data, the value of imports of used clothes skyrocketed by 607.6% (yoy) in January-September 2022. The following is a comparative graph of imports of used clothes and ready-made clothes.

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Figure 2. Comparison of import data
Source: Katadata, 2022

The people of Batam City use thrift clothing to fulfill primary needs. Apart from fulfilling needs, thrift clothing is also used as a trading business. The high public interest in the world of fashion has given rise to new ideas related to the thrifting business. Many factors influence consumers in their decision to purchase thrift clothing. Product quality is the main factor in the decision to purchase thrift clothing. According to Safitri Malik et al., (2022) Quality is influenced by a set of uses and benefits. including durability, independence, exclusivity of products and other components, comfort, appearance (color, shape, packaging, etc.). A purchasing decision is an activity carried out by a person when choosing a behavioral alternative from two or more and is estimated to be the right choice for the purchasing process. (Savira & Yulianti, 2022). In the process, purchasing decisions come from the consumer's decision to actually buy and use the product. In deciding to make a purchase, consumers are directly involved with the product they will use. There are various components of the purchasing decision process, namely price, product quality, promotion, E-WOM, lifestyle, and purchasing interest. According to Nadiya & Wahyuningsih (2020), price is the amount of money spent by consumers with the aim of being a means of exchange or exchange when they want to get a number of products/services as well as the benefits of the product or service that the consumer will get. By determining price values, the costs incurred in the production or distribution of a product or service. Factors that influence price determination include estimates between product demand and competitors' reactions, as well as the suitability of price to product value. The price component has an important role in the decision making process. Based on the background of this problem, researchers are interested in conducting further research regarding the factors that influence the people of Batam city in their decision to purchase Thrifting clothing products.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the collected articles listed in the literature review, the author is very interested in conducting research related to the variables Product Quality, Price, Lifestyle, Promotion, Electronic Word of Mouth, Purchase Intention on Purchase Decision.

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Based on the research model above, the development of hypotheses by researchers is as follows:

- H1: Product quality has a significant positive effect on Purchase Decision
- H2: Price has a significant positive effect on Purchase Decision
- H3: Lifestyle has a significant positive effect on Purchase Decision
- H4: Promotion has a significant positive effect on Purchase Decision
- H5: E-WOM has a significant positive effect on Purchase Decision
- H6: E-WOM has a significant positive effect on Purchase Intention
- H7: Purchase Intention has a significant positive effect on Purchase Decision
- H8 : Ewom influences purchase decisions which are mediated by purchase intention

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Design in research is used in methodology to structure research that ensures that ultimately one can draw certain types of conclusions. For example, starting with a random sample from a population is a step that could potentially be described in the research design section. This allows the study to assume that any differences between outcomes in the two groups are caused by the intervention. In this study, it can be grouped as comparative causal research, namely research to see the influence of one variable on another. This type of research has a relationship between the variables Product Quality, Price, Lifestyle, E-WOM (Electronic Word of Mouth) as independent, and the purchase decision is mediated by purchase intention. In this research, the research object that will be used is the people of Batam City. The samples used were residents of Batam City who had purchased Thrift clothing, either online (Instagram, Shopee, Ecommerce) or who had made purchases by coming directly to the Thrifting place (Thrift Market/Second Market). The targeted respondents are 400 respondents.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESPONDENT DEMOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

The data that has been collected in this research is 422 respondents out of the total number of respondents required, namely 400 respondents. This questionnaire was distributed and filled in by Batam City residents who had purchased Thrift (Second) clothing which was distributed in the form of a Google Form. Based on the data obtained, there were 317 female respondents, while there were 105 male respondents.

Table 4.1 Questionnaire Distribution Table

Information	Number of Respondents
Collected questionnaires	425
Questionnaires that are not filled out completely	3
Testable questionnaire	422

Source: Processed primary data (2023)

Based on the data above, it can be seen that 425 respondents were collected, the questionnaires filled out were incomplete/did not meet the criteria, namely 3 respondents. Therefore, the number of respondents who could be tested was 422 respondents.

Table 4.2 Table of respondents by gender

Respondent	Frequency	Percentage
Man	105	24.9%
Woman	317	75.1%
Total	422	100%

Source: Processed primary data (2023)

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Based on the data above, it can be seen that the majority of respondents who purchased Thrift clothing were 317 women or 75.1%. Meanwhile, 105 respondents were male. This shows that women are more likely to purchase Thrift clothing than men. Clothing is something that supports a woman's lifestyle. Apart from that, women are easily influenced by discounts, people around them, or public figures when buying something (Pritama, 2022).

Table 4.3 Respondents Based on Age

Respondent	Frequency	Percentage
< 20 Years	13	3.1%
20-25 Years	212	50.2%
26-30 Years	156	37%
31-39 Years	39	9.2%
> 40 Years	2	0.5%
Total	422	100%

Source: Processed primary data (2023)

Based on the data obtained, it can be seen that there were 13 respondents aged less than (<) 20 years, 212 people aged 20-25 years, 156 people aged 26-30 years, 39 people aged 31-39, and those aged > 40 years, namely 2 people. It can be seen that the majority of respondents who purchased Thrift clothing were respondents aged 20-25 years. Based on this data, it shows that people from the millennial generation and Gen Z like to buy Thrift clothing because they think that thrifting or shopping for used clothes is a suitable alternative or solution for those who like shopping but still want to protect the environment wisely.

Table 4.4 Respondents Based on Type of Work

Respondent	Frequency	Percentage
Private sector employee	221	52.4%
Government employees	40	9.5%
Self-employed	50	11.8%
Student/college student	104	24.6%
TNI/Polri	6	1.4%
Other	1	0.2%
Total	422	100%

Source: Processed primary data (2023)

Based on the data in table 4.4, it can be seen that the respondent data is based on occupation. Respondents were dominated by 221 private sector employees, 40 civil servants, 50 self-employed respondents, 104 students, 6 respondents for the TNI/Polri and 1 person for other jobs. This is because Thrift clothing purchases are dominated by private sector employees.

Table 4.5 Respondents Based on Monthly Income

Respondent	Frequency	Percentage
< Rp. 4,000,000	167	39.6%
IDR 4,000,000 – IDR 7,000,000	196	46.4%
IDR 7,000,000 – IDR 10,000,000	51	12.1%
> IDR 10,000,000	8	1.9%
Total	422	100%

Source: Processed primary data (2023)

Based on the data above, it can be seen that respondents have a variety of incomes, ranging from < IDR 4,000,000 to > IDR 10,000,000. The questionnaire was dominated by respondents with an income of IDR 4,000,000 – IDR. 7,000,000 as many as 196 respondents, while respondents with income < Rp. 4,000,000 as many as 167 respondents, respondents with an income of Rp. 7,000,000 – 10,000,000 as many as 51 respondents, and respondents with income > Rp. 10,000,000 as many as 8 people. This shows that because the price is very cheap, thrifting is popular with many groups (Nugraha, 2022), so that many people with various incomes like to buy Thrift clothing, Batam City's UMK is IDR 4,500,000. Thus, it can be concluded that the majority of respondents have incomes above the Batam City UMK.

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Table 4.6 Respondents Based on Thrift activities

Making a Thrift * Crosstabulation Thrift Place

Count

	Thrift Place	Online (Instagram, Facebook, Whatsapp & Ecommerce), directly at the location			Total
		Come directly to the place	Facebook, Ecommerce)	Whatsapp & Ecommerce)	
Making Thrifts Once		137	140	145	422
Total		137	140	145	422

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

Based on the data in table 4.6, it can be seen that as many as 422 respondents have purchased clothes *Thrift*. When purchasing, respondents can come directly to the location, or buy online. Based on the table above, it can be seen that the majority of respondents often buy Thrift clothing online (via Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, & Ecommerce) as many as 140 respondents, and respondents who buy directly come to the place as many as 137 respondents, while 145 respondents choose both places to choose from. buy thrift clothes, either online or in person.

4.2.1 Outer Model Evaluation

4.2.1.1 Outer Loadings & AVE Test Results

It can be seen in table 4.7 that the data from the outer loadings test results from 422 respondents who met the criteria were declared valid. This is because each variable has a high level of correlation and exceeds 0.6.

Table 4.7 Outer Loadings Test Results

	EWOM	Lifestyle	Price	Product Quality	Promotion	Purchase Intention	Purchase Decision
PQ1				0.809			
PQ2				0.772			
PQ3				0.611			
PQ4				0.734			
PQ5				0.853			
PRI1			0.812				
PRI2			0.769				
PRI3			0.792				
PRI4			0.739				
L1		0.495					
L2		0.781					
L3		0.845					
L4		0.806					
PRO1					0.818		
PRO2					0.842		
PRO3					0.778		
EWOM1	0.791						
EWOM2	0.777						
EWOM3	0.773						
EWOM4	0.837						
PI1						0.827	
PI2						0.801	
PI3						0.828	
WW1							0.766
WW2							0.775
PD3							0.753
PD4							0.733
PD5							0.798
PD6							0.814
PD7							0.791

Source: Processed primary data (2023)

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The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value is >0.5 to be said to be valid and meets the convergent validity requirements so that data testing can be continued to the next level. It can be seen in table 4.8, the results of the AVE data test carried out are declared valid and have exceeded 0.5.

Table 4.8 AVE Data Test Results

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Information
<i>Electronic Word Of Mouth</i>	0.632	Valid
<i>Lifestyle</i>	0.555	Valid
<i>Price</i>	0.606	Valid
<i>Product Quality</i>	0.578	Valid
<i>Promotion</i>	0.661	Valid
<i>Purchase Intention</i>	0.671	Valid
<i>Purchase Decision</i>	0.62	Valid

Source: Primary data processed (2023)

4.2.2 Discriminant Validity Test Results

4.2.2.1 Cross Loadings Test Results and Fornell Larcker Criterion

One test of discriminant validity can use the cross loading indicator and the Fornell Larcker Criterion with a value of >0.7 between the same variables Ghozali (2016). It can be seen in table 4.9 and table 4.10, that the results of the discriminant validity test carried out were declared valid and exceeded 0.7.

Table 4.9 Cross Loadings Test Results

	Electronic word of mouth	Lifestyle	Price	Product Quality	Promotion	Purchase Intention	Purchase decisions
PQ1	0.336	0.287	0.290	0.809	0.123	0.197	0.285
PQ2	0.327	0.285	0.325	0.772	0.128	0.156	0.262
PQ3	0.179	0.233	0.254	0.611	0.093	0.108	0.172
PQ4	0.214	0.252	0.329	0.734	0.121	0.224	0.235
PQ5	0.427	0.331	0.320	0.853	0.219	0.284	0.406
PRI1	0.276	0.345	0.812	0.308	0.255	0.403	0.285
PRI2	0.359	0.341	0.769	0.343	0.273	0.388	0.337
PRI3	0.256	0.361	0.792	0.270	0.228	0.361	0.265
PRI4	0.253	0.334	0.739	0.304	0.204	0.430	0.232
L1	0.119	0.495	0.282	0.207	0.125	0.348	0.204
L2	0.304	0.781	0.418	0.347	0.334	0.400	0.357
L3	0.330	0.845	0.370	0.292	0.335	0.436	0.419
L4	0.321	0.806	0.269	0.256	0.312	0.347	0.412
PRO1	0.197	0.337	0.300	0.135	0.818	0.359	0.335
PRO2	0.222	0.322	0.255	0.182	0.842	0.351	0.372
PRO3	0.167	0.285	0.198	0.146	0.778	0.259	0.268
EWOM1	0.791	0.311	0.338	0.308	0.147	0.289	0.396
EWOM2	0.777	0.350	0.299	0.365	0.204	0.292	0.409
EWOM3	0.773	0.272	0.243	0.307	0.198	0.344	0.379
EWOM4	0.837	0.273	0.311	0.331	0.222	0.285	0.455
PI1	0.388	0.382	0.306	0.309	0.302	0.414	0.766
PI2	0.428	0.396	0.271	0.296	0.317	0.451	0.775
PI3	0.355	0.318	0.343	0.284	0.318	0.461	0.753
WW1	0.386	0.343	0.296	0.249	0.316	0.419	0.733
WW2	0.402	0.357	0.238	0.266	0.289	0.447	0.798
PD3	0.442	0.383	0.209	0.306	0.320	0.451	0.814
PD4	0.398	0.433	0.328	0.337	0.337	0.532	0.791
PD5	0.340	0.380	0.472	0.239	0.309	0.827	0.462
PD6	0.281	0.465	0.393	0.258	0.305	0.801	0.477
PD7	0.313	0.401	0.378	0.167	0.372	0.828	0.502

Source: Processed primary data (2023)

The method for testing discriminant validity is cross loading which requires that the same indicators must converge or be highly correlated with the respective variables with a value of at least 0.7 or > 0.7 . Based on table 4.9, although several indicators have

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values <0.7 , these indicators are highly correlated with each variable. For this reason, it can be stated that all variables have met the cross loading criteria.

Table 4.10 Fornell Larcker Criterion Test Results.

	EWOM	Lifestyle	Price	Product Quality	Promotion	Purchase Intention	Purchase Decision
EWOM	0.795						
Lifestyle	0.378	0.745					
Price	0.374	0.443	0.779				
Product Quality	0.412	0.369	0.397	0.760			
Promotion	0.243	0.388	0.312	0.191	0.813		
Purchase Intention	0.380	0.506	0.506	0.269	0.402	0.819	
Purchase Decision	0.516	0.483	0.366	0.378	0.405	0.586	0.776

Discriminant validity is good and meets the criteria if the square root of AVE for each construct is greater than the correlation between constructs in the model. Based on table 4.10, it can be indicated that all variables have met the criteria because all the correlations between indicators in the model are not greater when compared with the correlations between indicators on the variables themselves.

4.2.2.2 Discriminant Validity - Hetetotrait Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Another method that can be used to test discriminant validity is Hetetotrait Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). The HTMT value is declared to have met discriminant validity when it is <0.90 . This value is also included in the excellent value. Based on table 4.11, it can be seen that all correlation values between constructs are less than 0.90, so it can be stated that the data has met the discriminant validity criteria.

Table 4.11 Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) Test Results

	EWOM	Lifestyle	Price	Product Quality	Promotion	Purchase Intention	Purchase Decision
EWOM							
Lifestyle	0.477						
Price	0.462	0.601					
Product Quality	0.479	0.482	0.493				
Promotion	0.309	0.505	0.397	0.226			
Purchase Intention	0.488	0.702	0.659	0.325	0.527		
Purchase Decision	0.608	0.585	0.430	0.417	0.490	0.714	

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

4.2.3.1 Reliability Test Results

A variable is declared reliable if it meets Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values > 0.70 . Based on the results of the reliability test in table 4.12, it can be seen that all variables are reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values of all variables have shown > 0.70 .

Table 4.12 Cronbach's Alpha & Composite Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
Electronic word of mouth	0.805	0.873	Reliable
Lifestyle	0.724	0.828	Reliable
Price	0.785	0.860	Reliable
Product Quality	0.820	0.871	Reliable
Promotion	0.746	0.854	Reliable
Purchase Intention	0.754	0.859	Reliable
Purchase decisions	0.890	0.914	Reliable

4.2.4 Inner Model (Structural Model Evaluation)

In testing the inner model data, the first stage that will be carried out is testing the direct effect data. Regarding the provisions, if the number in the T-Statistic is >1.96 , it means it is significant, if the number is less than 1.96, then the sign is not significant. Then, the P-Value value <0.05 means significant, if it is more than 0.05 then the hypothesis is declared not significant Ghozali (2021).

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Table 4.13 Path Coefficient Test Results (Direct Effect)

Hypothesis	Sample Mean	T-Statistics	P-Values	Information
Electronic word of mouth -> Purchase Intention	0.384	6,053	0.000	Significant Positive
Electronic word of mouth -> Purchase decision	0.274	3,081	0.002	Significant Positive
Lifestyle -> Purchase decisions	0.110	1,132	0.258	Not significant
Price -> Purchase decision	-0.063	1,201	0.230	Not significant
Product Quality -> Purchase decision	0.123	1,546	0.123	Not significant
Promotion -> Purchase decision	0.143	2,180	0.030	Significant Positive
Purchase Intention -> Purchase decision	0.371	3,442	0.001	Significant Positive

Source: Processed primary data (2023)

Based on the results of data testing in table 4.13, there are several statements for the hypothesis that have been made and are explained as follows:

Hypothesis 1:

Based on the data in table 4.13, it can be seen that *Product Quality* does not have a significant effect on Purchase decisions. Judging from the results, the sample mean is 0.123 and the p-values are 0.123, which means the hypothesis is rejected. This is in line with research Nadiya & Wahyuningsih (2020), related to Second Fashion Purchase Decisions on the Marketplace. It can be seen that if product quality decreases, it will affect consumer purchasing decisions. Buying used clothes does have a high risk, because if you are not careful when buying, there could be unknown product defects.

Hypothesis 2:

Based on the data in table 4.13, it can be seen that price does not have a significant effect on purchase decisions. Judging from the results, the sample mean is -0.063 and the p-values are 0.230, which means the hypothesis is rejected. This is in line with research conducted by Shofiyana (2020). This can be proven by the increase in prices given by sellers, because the used clothes being bought and sold are branded clothes from abroad. According to CNN (2022), the price comparison of new clothes and used clothes is only slightly different, therefore, consumers prefer to use new clothes compared to Thrift clothes.

Hypothesis 3:

Based on the data in table 4.13, it can be seen that Lifestyle does not have a significant effect on Purchase decision. Judging from the results, the sample mean is 0.110 and p-values are 0.258, which means the hypothesis is rejected. This is supported by research Mongisidi et al (2019), who conducted research related to the influence of lifestyle and price on purchasing decisions for Nike shoes. This is proven that each person's lifestyle is different. Lifestyle includes the way consumers interact with each other. From time to time, lifestyle can change. In this case, the difference in consumer lifestyle is towards wearing Thrift clothing and preferring to wear new clothing. So it can be concluded that Lifestyle has no influence on consumer purchasing decisions.

Hypothesis 4:

In table 4.13, you can see the test results which state that Promotion has a direct influence on Purchase Decision. This can be seen in the sample mean figure of 0.143 and p-values of 0.030. This states that the influence is positive and significant. This is supported by research conducted by Hasan & Leon (2022) related to promotions for seafood customers in Batam City. This is proven that promotions that are carried out well will attract a wider range of customers. Promotion is a tool used by sellers to communicate with potential buyers. By showing the advantages of the product, it attracts potential customers.

Hypothesis 5:

In table 4.13, you can see the test results which state that E-WOM has a direct influence on Purchase Decisions. This can be seen in the sample mean figure of 0.274 and p-values of 0.002. This states that the influence is positive and significant. This is in line with research Ayunita (2021) who conducted research related to the influence of promotions and EWOM on Thythy online shop purchasing decisions. EWOM is carried out online on social media. Implementing EWOM can be done by assessing a product, or sharing stories on social media with the general public. Therefore, EWOM influences consumer purchasing decisions.

Hypothesis 6:

In table 4.13, you can see the test results which state that E-WOM has a direct influence on Purchase Intention. This can be seen in the sample mean figure of 0.384 and p-values of 0.000. This states that the influence is positive and significant. This is in line with research Yudanegara & Rahmi, (2019) related to the influence of EWOM on Purchase Intention among MSMEs in Bandung City. EWOM applied to social media can have an influence on purchasing interest. Seeing or hearing other people's assessments of a product can increase potential consumers' buying interest.

Hypothesis 7:

In table 4.13, you can see the test results which state that Purchase Intention has a direct influence on Purchase Decision. This can be seen in the sample mean figure of 0.371 and p-values of 0.001. This states that the influence is positive and significant. This is supported by research Afifi & Wahyuni (2019). This is proven by the higher the level of purchasing interest generated, the greater the

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opportunity to make a purchasing decision. Purchase interest will arise after there are other alternative choices regarding the choice of a product. So buying interest influences purchasing decisions.

4.2.5 Indirect Effect Test Results (Indirect Influence)

The indirect effect test results play a role in showing the role of mediating variables in research. There is a provision that the t-statistic number >1.96 will be declared significant. Then p-values <0.05 will indicate significance.

Table 4.14 Indirect effect test results.

	Sample Mean	T-Statistics	P-Values	Information
Electronic word of mouth -> Purchase Intention -> Purchase decision	0.143	2,909	0.004	Significant positive

Source: Processed primary data (2023)

Hypothesis 8:

In table 4.13, you can see the test results which state that EWOM influences purchase decisions which are mediated by purchase intention. This can be seen in the sample mean figure of 0.143 and p-values of 0.004. This states that the influence is positive and significant. Backed by research Luthfiyatillah et al, (2020) This happens because purchasing decisions are based on purchasing intentions from external influences, needs and awareness in product introduction. Purchasing decisions are the process of determining the choice of two alternative options. In understanding consumer purchasing intentions, you must understand customer needs and desires. Customers tend to trust and believe in other people's decisions before buying a product.

4.2.6 Determining Coefficient Test Results (R2)

Based on the data processing carried out, there are results in table 4.14 which displays the R Square value for the Purchase variable with a value of 0.640 which indicates that this variable is strong enough and the R Square for the Purchase Decision variable is 0.486 which indicates that this variable is not strong enough. It can be concluded that these two variables are not strong enough against the other variables

Table 4.14 Square test result

	R Square Adjusted
Purchase Intention	0.143
Purchase decisions	0.485

Source: Processed primary data (2023)

V. CONCLUSION

Product Quality does not have a significant effect on Purchase decisions. If product quality decreases, it will affect consumer purchasing decisions. Buying used clothes does have a high risk, because if you are not careful when buying, there could be unknown product defects. Price does not have a significant effect on Purchase decisions. There is an increase in prices given by sellers, because the used clothes being bought and sold are branded clothes from abroad. The price comparison for new clothes and used clothes is only slightly different, therefore, consumers prefer to use new clothes compared to Thrift clothes. Lifestyle does not have a significant effect on Purchase decisions. From time to time, lifestyle can change. In this case, the difference in consumer lifestyle is towards wearing Thrift clothing and preferring to wear new clothing. So it can be concluded that Lifestyle has no influence on consumer purchasing decisions. Promotion has a direct influence on Purchase Decision. Promotions that are carried out well will attract a wider range of customers. Promotion is a tool used by sellers to communicate with potential buyers. By showing the advantages of the product, it attracts potential customers.

E-WOM has a direct influence on Purchase Decision. EWOM is carried out online on social media. Implementing EWOM can be done by assessing a product, or sharing stories on social media with the general public. Therefore, EWOM influences consumer purchasing decisions. E-WOM has a direct influence on Purchase Intention. EWOM applied to social media can have an influence on purchasing interest. Seeing or hearing other people's assessments of a product can increase potential consumers' buying interest. Purchase Intention has a direct influence on Purchase Decision. The higher the level of purchasing interest generated, the greater the opportunity to make a purchasing decision. Purchase interest will arise after there are other alternative choices regarding the choice of a product. So buying interest influences purchasing decisions. EWOM influences purchase decisions which are mediated by purchase intention. This happens because purchasing decisions are based on purchasing intentions from external influences, needs and awareness in product introduction. Purchasing decisions are the process of determining the choice of two alternative options. In understanding consumer purchasing intentions, you must understand customer needs and desires. Customers tend to trust and believe in other people's decisions before buying a product.

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